

1 **Transformation by homeobox genes involves silencing of the death receptor TNFRSF21 and CDKN**
2 **cell cycle inhibitors.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We studied the transcriptome of human cells depleted of the master oncogenic homeobox factor *PAX8* to
8 identify genes that functioned in induction of transformation in cancer cells and maintenance of the
9 transformed state in a tumor. The death receptor DR6, encoded by TNFRSF21, was isolated as a
10 conserved effector of homeobox-induced transformation. Consistent with a function for TNFRSF21
11 regulation of survival during and support of cell death evasion by silencing of TNFRSF21 in cancer,
12 TNFRSF21 activation was identified as a central transcriptional component of the gene expression
13 program in an *in vitro* model of senescence in human cells, and TNFRSF21 silencing was a signature
14 transcriptional change of the transcriptomes of tumor cells in humans with blood cancer resulting from
15 expression of an KMT2A- MLL4 fusion oncogene or a Nup98-NSD1 fusion oncogene. Systems biological
16 approaches indicated TNFRSF21 might function through interactions with BCL family apoptotic regulators
17 BCL2L2 and BOK. We have now described three discrete mechanisms by which homeoboxes maintain
18 the hallmark behaviors that define the cancer cell: induction of growth factors that sustain proliferative
19 ability by licensing derestricted cell cycle progression, evasion of oncogene-induced senescence through
20 bypass of cell-intrinsic cell cycle inhibition and of tumor surveillance that occurs through induction of
21 interferon-stimulated genes in senescence, and through regulation of cell death signals transduced by
22 death receptors.
23
24
25
26
27
28